

that thought as evolved by three great Muslim thinkers. Two of them, Ibn abi'r Rabi' and Farabi lived and wrote in the period called the Dark ages in Europe when there was hardly a speck of political speculation in the West, while Ibn K'haldun, who wrote as late as the fourteenth century A.C. was a prince of thinkers among his contemporaries, and compares favourably even with some of those who came after him. In the footnotes a comparison is attempted between what they wrote and the political thought of Europe centuries after. Within the short compass of an article it is not possible to discuss more of Muslim political thought, but there is a chain of Muslims who enlightened the world by their ideas and who were the forerunners of the fathers of modern political speculation in the West.

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MUHAMMADABAD-KALPI AND ITS HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Turkish conquest of Bundelkhand : When Mahmud of Ghazni raided Hindustan the main resistance to the Ghaznavide arms in the Ganga-Jamuna valley came not from the Imperial Pratiharas of Kanauj but from their nominal but more powerful vassals the Chandelas of Kalinjar who ruled the country south of the Jamuna from the Chambal in the west to the Son in the east. The second Doab campaign of Mahmud (1019) had been directed against the ruler of Kalinjar (بيدا Vidya) and again (1022) the forts of Gwalior and Kalinjar were invested with a view to forcing a conclusion.

The death of Mahmud weakened the Turkish pressure on the Indian plains and by the middle of the (eleventh) century the Chandelas too were eclipsed for a time by the Kalachuris. By the close of the century the Kalachuris collapsed and the Gaharivalas began ruling in Kanauj. There was a revival of Chandela power during the first half of the 12th century but Prthviraja Chauhan gave a rude shock to the Chandela power in 1182-83 and when the Chauhan barrier was broken at Tarain (1191-2), Gwalior was besieged by Mui'zzuddin ibn Sam and ultimately surrendered to Malik Aibak in 1200 who attacked the heart of the Chandela country (1202-3) and Kalinjar. Mahoba and Khajuraho were grouped under Delhi into a military division. But the Chandelas continued to rule south of Kalinjar which was soon lost to them along with Gwalior which had to be again reduced by Iltutmish (1232). From Gwalior Nusratuddin Tayasi led a raid to the "country of Kalinjar" (1233-4). After Iltutmish there was a general recovery of the Rajputs and the land of the Chandelas was still a *terra incognita* to the Turks in spite of Ulugh Khan Balban's campaign against the mysterious "Dalki-wa-Malki" and a full-fledged expedition against Chahardeva of Narwar whose successors continued to rule from Gwalior. It was given to Alauddin to effect a permanent reduction of these territories and we find the army of Malik Kafur staying for four days at Sultanpur-Erachh on their way to the Warangal campaign. Under the early Tughluqs, Mahoba was a minor charge bracketed with Kare but under Firuz Shah it is mentioned as an independent iqta'.

MALIKZADA FIRUZ KHAN-I-JAHAN

Shiq Firuzpur: Malik Chhatta, a favourite slave of Prince Fath Khan (d.1376), fled to the Chauhans and this was the beginning of the Chauhan trouble in the Doab which constituted a permanent source of anxiety to the Delhi Sultans for a century. The potentiality of the Chauhans for future trouble seems to have been sufficiently gauged by Firuz Tughluq for he undertook two excursions to Itawa. In 1377 he founded the fortress of Tughluqpur near Itawa as the headquarters of a military division with the stations south of the Jamuna as its dependencies. Again in 1379 the headquarters had to be changed to Firuzpur on the Jamuna, opposite Kanar, with Malikzada Firuz as the governor of *Shiq Firuzpur*.

Malikzada Firuz was the son of Malik Tajuddin Turk, Naib of Gujarat under Mubarak Khalji and Tughluq Shah. Malikzada Firuz rose under the auspices of Firuz Shah. He was deputed to persuade the Jam of *Thattha* and Bamaniya to meet the Sultan. As governor of *Shiq Firuzpur* he led a campaign against the Rai of Gagraun in North Malwa but, entrusting the military forces of *Shiq Firuzpur* to the command of his eldest son, Malikzada Mahmud, he stayed at the capital as a prominent member of the Jauna clique. After the murder of the Vizier he succeeded to his office and title and on the demise of the Sultan, he tried to win support for Tughluq Shah II but failed and perished along with his master (1389).

Rai Sumer (Suber) Sah of Itawa and his ally, Rawat Adharan, younger brother of the Gwalior Rai, had been carried to Delhi with their family and dependants, by Firuz Shah on his second visit to Itawa and we find them occupying a back seat on the floor in his durbar. In the civil war they joined Prince Muhammad Khan but finally came down to *Shiq Firuzpur*, set the authority of Malikzada Mahmud at naught and inflicted a defeat on his forces. In spite of reinforcements brought from Delhi by his brothers, Mahmud lost the whole of the middle Doab to the Rajputs, moved from Firuzpur to Kalpi south of the Jamuna, christened it Muhammadabad (1390) and became virtually independent. Two years later when Sultan Muhammad Shah led a punitive expedition against Sumer and Adharan, Mahmud joined the imperial forces from Kalpi and was confirmed in *Shiq Firuzpur* (now Kalpi) with the iqta' of Mahoba added to it.

NASIR-UD DIN MAHMUD SHAH 1390-1411

Mahmud was the greatest ruler of the Malikzada dynasty of the Sultan-Amirs of Kalpi. He fully subjugated the Mahoba country between the Betwa and the Ken and cleared it of the Rajput menace from the east by punishing the Rajputs of the Ken-Bagain valley and by

raiding the country of the Baghela chief of Gahora-Biram, "the Niram of the Age," the illustrious ancestor of H.H. the Maharaja of Rewa when Arail and Prayag were plundered and pilgrims of the holy place taken captives.

In the Erachh country the rebel governor had summoned the aid of Rai Sumer of Itawa but, thanks to the arrival of Dilawar Khan, the ruler of Dhar, who wished to repay an obligation to the Malikzada family, the strategic fort of Erachh was saved and along with it the prestige of Kalpi. Erachh, first included among the household iqtas, was later assigned to Junaid Khan, next brother and Vizier. Jatahra, to the far south, was assigned likewise to the third brother, Nizam Khan.

After the pacification of his territories, when Kalpi began to attract the learned classes and the nobility of Delhi, Mahmud turned to the Chauhans of *Shiq Firuzpur* who had colonies throughout the modern districts of Etawah, Mainpuri and Etah. Their leader was Rai Sumer Sah of Itawa. Another stock were the Chauhans of Chandwar (South Agra), called Bhadauriya, who had founded the principality of Hathkant between the Jamuna and the Chambal. The Rathors of Khor-Shamsabad and Kampil (North Farrukhabad) were allied to the Chauhans and their joint turbulence had turned the entire middle Doab into a sort of "no man's land. Malik Muqarrab-ul-Mulk, at the instance of Sultan Muhammad II, "preferring strategem to strategy", had enticed the leaders to the fort of Kanauj and had them perfidiously murdered. But the arch-rebel Sumer had escaped and lived, for the next thirty years, to carry on his undaunted depredations. Itawa had become an easy place of refuge for Kalpi rebels and Mahmud, in his first expedition, raided Itawa and Hathkant of the Chauhans and Gwalior of their Tomar allies. On the second occasion Mahmud sat down to reduce Itawa, stayed for the rains in Kanar with the determination to resume the siege after the rains but did not live to accomplish his object.

Thus died in harness Malikzada Mahmud, the founder of the Kalpi House. The Chauhan menace could not be entirely eliminated but Mahmud had given stability to his dominions by dividing them into seven iqta's, besides Kalpi proper, which constituted the reserved area (اقطاع خاص). That effective possession over the Doab was lost, was not Mahmud's fault. After Timur's invasion he had assumed the insignia of royalty and Mahmud Shah, the last Tughluq sovereign, while proceeding from Kanauj to Delhi to occupy his ancestral throne (1405), had sent the canopy, 'durbash' and 'tas' for his Kalpi namesake with the title of Sultan and he is spoken of as such in the inscription of the Jami' Masjid of Erachh. The author of the *Tarikh-i-Muhammadi* calls him "Nasir-ud Din Mahmud Shah. During his lifetime Kalpi had become a cultural centre with the migration there of the 'U'lama' and *Mashaikh* from Delhi. Maulana Khwajgi, "unrivalled in learning," a disciple of *Shaikh* Nasir-uddin Chiragh-i-Delhi, in anticipation of the Mughul invasion, had

settled in Kalpi and Maulana Ahmad *Thanesari*, "master of prose and poetry," who drafted the letters of Sultan Firuz to Timur, came after the invasion and gave lessons to students in Kalpi. Both lie buried there, the former outside the fort and the latter inside it where a dome was raised over his grave by his disciple, Ahmad *Khan*, youngest brother of Sultan Mahmud.

IKHTIYAR-UD DIN QADIR SHAH, 1411-32

Qadir *Shah* had been commander and muster-master of the Kalpi forces during the reign of his father. Rai Sumer Chauhan was at the zenith of his power now and Qadir lost the battle of Jagdaha in the Doab against him with the result that Sumer reappeared before Kalpi but was defeated and the forces of the Rai of Gwalior, who was advancing to join hands with Sumer, were also repulsed. The Naib of Chandari (Malwa) who had occupied Panyargarh, a dependency of Jatahra, was compelled to disgorge his usurpation.

At this juncture Junaid *Khan*, the veteran Vizier and the builder of the Jami Masjid of Erachh, who had been the mainstay of the kingdom, died and was succeeded by his elder son, Daulat *Khan*, to his office and assignment. During the regime of the new Vizier, Rai Sumer and other rais and Muqaddams became friendly with Qadir *Shah*, who obliged Sumer by raiding Bhuingaon in the Doab held by Sumer's collaterals of the senior branch. But this was only a lull before the coming storm. Sultan Ibrahim *Sharqi* of Jaunpur marched to Kalpi with his army and elephants with the intention of conquering it (1413). Ibrahim may have espoused the cause of some Kalpi rebels after the friendly behaviour of Sumer towards Qadir. But the strategic position of Kalpi state as a buffer against Malwa and a stepping-stone to Delhi was the real cause of the invasion. Ibrahim occupied Mahoba, Rath and Shahpur and deputed his minister (Vizier), muster-master (arid) and Biramdeo Baghela of Gahora, who had become an ally of the *Sharqis*, to attack the strong fortress of Erachh held by Bihamad *Khan*, father of the author of the *Tarikh-i-Muhammadi*, who has given a graphic eyewitness account of the brave but desperate defence put up by the commander who had shut himself up in the citadel. In a hand-to-hand fight with the enemy Bihamad was severely wounded, his wife was killed and his son (the author) received a grievous injury in his arm.

The fall of Erachh was a prelude to the reduction of the dependencies—Bhanrer and Jatahra—and Ibrahim, who was directing the operation from Kalpi now rose to attack the fort of the capital with manjaniq and ar-rada but Qadir *Shah* accepted the vassalage of Jaunpur, thinking discretion to be the better part of valour. Echoes of the Kalpi hostilities had reached the powerless Daulat *Khan* Lodi, master of Delhi, but Qadir *Shah* himself had strength enough to reassert his authority over the districts as soon as the back of the *Sharqi* Sultan was turned. Qadir *Shah's*

marriage with the sister of Sultan Hoshang of Malwa was most probably contracted during this period ostensibly as a check against a possible aggression of Jaunpur in the future.

Vizier Daulat *Khan* now died and was succeeded in his office and emoluments by his younger brother, Mubarak *Khan*. There seems to have been a lull in military activities for a long time. Towards the end of his reign Qadir *Shah* led a campaign against the chiefs of Sihunra and Simauni when Rai Tas, the powerful Bais chief of Dhundiakhera (Unao District) on the frontiers of Jaunpur, came to their aid with his equally famous son, Sathan, father of the celebrated Rai Tilokchand of Baksar. His attack was repulsed and hostilities were carried into his own territories in the Doab as far as Bithur.

Qadir *Shah* was a valiant prince and he was well served by his collaterals of Erachh and Jatahra in the difficult times when the Doab of *Shiq* Firuzpur had passed to the hegemony of Jaunpur which had become a standing menace to the very existence of Kalpi. Qadir *Shah* may have entertained faint hopes of possible help from the Sayyid rulers of Delhi, for we find him sending timely information to Sultan Mubarak *Shah* (1428) of the march of Ibrahim *Sharqi* towards Delhi.

FATH-UD-DIN JALAL SHAH 1432-43.

At the death of Qadir *Shah*, Kalpi seems to have owed allegiance to Malwa for we are informed by Muhammad Bihamad *Khani* that the principal nobles seated Jalal *Khan*, the second son of Qadir (from the sister of Sultan Hoshang), on "the masnad of Imarat" in preference to the eldest, Nasir *Khan*, who thereupon joined Ibrahim *Sharqi* and was honoured by him with the title of *Khan-i-Jahan*. But Jalal *Khan* was a worthless person. He was very soon deposed for his misdeeds by the nobles and sent to Chandari in the dominions of his royal uncle. Thus both Jaunpur and Malwa had an excuse furnished for interfering in Kalpi affairs. Ibrahim marched to Kalpi (1433) and was soon followed by Hoshang, each in support of his own candidate. Jalal *Khan* was reseated on the masnad of Kalpi and Nasir *Khan* in the fort of Shahpur and both Sultans retired within the limits of their own dominions for the rains. Ibrahim *Sharqi's* movements were very cautious for he had heard of the mobilization of the Delhi forces by Sultan Mubarak *Shah* just before his assassination. After the rains Hoshang, joined by his protege, Jalal *Khan*, crossed the Jamuna into the *Sharqi* territories but after some skirmishes beat a sudden retreat to his own kingdom, leaving Jalal to his fate. Jalal, in the meantime, had alienated the nobles by the murder of Nizam *Khan* and on the approach of Ibrahim *Sharqi* near Kalpi, evacuated the fort. Nasir *Khan-i-Jahan*, his hopes frustrated now left the company of Sultan Ibrahim who felt it advisable to transfer his patronage to Jalal *Khan*. This was not relished by the nobles. Mubarak *Khan*, the ex-Vizier, assumed independence in Erachh and

Ismail Khan, son of Nizam Khan, in Jatahra, their kinship being further reinforced by a marriage bond. Nasir Khan-i-Jahan retired to Rath and Mahoba and there in his retreat he bided his time in sullen disaffection only to reappear in Kalpi at the right moment as a claimant for the masnad which was his by birthright. As for Jalal he seems to have been content with his shrunken possessions north of the Betwa and after the death of Ibrahim Sharqi (1436) we find him striking coins with the title of Fath-ud Din Jalal Shah.

NASIR SHAH 1443-C. 1451

The reign of Nasir Shah coincides with the careers of Mahmud Khalji of Mandu and his namesake of Jaunpur when Kalpi was still regarded as a dependency of Malwa. In 1443 it was reported to Mahmud Khalji that Nasir was an apostate and a tyrant and the Sharqi Sultan, securing the tacit approval of Malwa by means of presents for the punishment of mischief, marched to Kalpi. Nasir, who had already sent a denial of the charges, appealed for support to Mahmud Khalji who interceded on his behalf without effect. In the meantime Nasir had been ousted from Kalpi and made a second appeal to Malwa. Mahmud Khalji, joined by Nasir at Chanderi, marched to Kalpi where an indecisive battle was fought. But Mahmud Khalji, like Hoshang Shah on the last occasion, suspended hostilities and retired within his own territorial limits for the rains. Mahmud Sharqi's anxiety was to prevent the fort of Erachh from falling to Malwa and when diversionary tactics failed, he appealed to Shaikh Chayalda, the pir of the Malwa Sultan and through his intervention the Treaty of Erachh stopped the war. Rath and Mahoba were handed over to Nasir Shah immediately and after four months, when his religious faith had been tested, Kalpi with its dependencies followed. Thus did the Sharqi king manage to save his face in his differences with the greatest Sultan of Malwa, and Kalpi continued to be a sphere of Malwan influence.

MAHMUD SHAH II C. 1451-86

After the death of Mahmud Khalji, Kalpi became a Jaunpur dependency under Hussain Shah Sharqi from whom it was conquered by Bahlul Lodi who replaced the last ruler, Mahmud Shah, by his grandson A'zam Humayun.

Conclusion:—The political condition of India in the 15th century has been compared to that of Renaissance Italy—a congeries of states, big and small (J. I. H. XXVI, 223), of which minor dynasties, like their Italian prototypes, were centres of literature and art and exerted not a little influence on the power politics of the country. Kalpi, situated between the powerful kingdoms of Jaunpur and Malwa,

was treated by Malwa as a buffer state against Jaunpur and by Jaunpur as a stepping stone for the conquest of Delhi.

The State of Kalpi, extending between the Sindh in the Gwalior region and the Ken in the Kalinjar tract, corresponded the Jhansi division of Uttar Pradesh coupled with the Bundelkhand Division of Vindhya Pradesh. The revenue of Kalpi in the time of Babar was 4,28,55,950 Sikandaris which, worked out in terms of the modern coin, would amount to two and three quarter crores before World War II.

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Genealogical Table of the Malikzada Dynasty of Kalpi

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[And say : My Lord ! Increase me in knowledge.—Qur'an]

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